

Capacitor-based Medium Voltage Test System for DC Circuit Breakers

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Abstract—This paper studies the design of a capacitor-based 12 kV test circuit for evaluating the performance of DC Circuit Breakers (DCCB) in Medium Voltage DC (MVDC) applications. The proposed circuit offers a cost-effective solution for realistic testing in research laboratories. It also accommodates current reversal during interruption, as required with latest DCCB technologies. The paper details the key test circuit requirements, component selection process, and a comprehensive PSCAD simulation model. The simulation model analyzes the operation of both the test circuit and DCCB under various test conditions, including charging circuit performance, discharge circuit response with the DCCB closed, and fault current interruption with different current thresholds. The results demonstrate that the MV DCCB test circuit achieves the desired peak current, its derivative, and energy, while post-fault voltage stress is lower than in real circuits.

Keywords—DC Circuit Breakers, MVDC, DCCB Test Circuit.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing adoption of renewable energy, storage technologies, and electrification across various industries is driving the growth of Medium Voltage DC (MVDC) systems. As these systems become more prominent, the need for reliable protection and control mechanisms including DC Circuit Breakers (DCCBs) becomes paramount [1], [2].

While DCCBs have been utilized in the railway industry at lower voltages for many years, these technologies are not suitable for MVDC or HVDC systems. In parallel, there has been significant development of High Voltage DC (HVDC) transmission grids and their DCCBs, which are crucial for minimizing peak fault currents, facilitating faster system restoration, and reducing the risk of converter station outages [2] [3] [4] [5].

There is plethora of different DCCB technologies, and lot of ongoing research and development of new devices. Hybrid DCCBs offer rapid operating times within 2-3 ms, but their reliance on high-voltage semiconductor valves significantly increases their cost [5]. Conversely, mechanical DCCBs utilizing primarily electromechanical components, offer a more cost-effective solution but suffer from slower operating times around 8-10 ms [6]. Recently, a novel LC DCCB topology utilising capacitor in parallel with mechanical components has been proposed [7], demonstrating promising performance and competitive costs, thereby showing significant potential for medium and high voltage applications. The LC DCCB concept has been demonstrated in laboratory settings at lower voltages (5kV) [7].

Testing DCCBs under realistic conditions is essential for validating their performance. In general, DCCB test circuit should provide adequate Voltage, Current and Energy stress,

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to evaluate the breakers' performance. A particular challenge comparing with AC CBs, is the energy dissipation in DCCBs [8]. One common testing approach utilizes charged capacitors to generate the required peak fault current [5]. However, it suffers from significant voltage drop during capacitor discharge, leading to insufficient voltage stress on DCCB and limiting the ability to test re-closure. Another approach [4],[6],[8] is to use existing test circuits for AC CBs which assume DC voltage and current stress in a half cycle, depending on DCCB operating speed and AC frequency. While it can achieve the desired peak current, the voltage typically drops significantly within a short timeframe, limiting the ability to evaluate the DCCB's dielectric strength. This is resolved using 2-stage testing where additional capacitor provides post-interruption voltage stress [8]. Reference [3] proposed an approach that solely relies on current source to provide the desired current profile, considering that key DCCB performance indicator is the peak interrupting current. A DC chopper-based approach is proposed in [8] and implemented at 1 kV. Although it is able to adequately test the breaker's dielectric strength and achieve several reclosures, it is not cost effective for MV or higher voltage applications.

This paper presents design of a 12kV capacitor-based test circuit intended for MV DCCB testing at University laboratory. Despite the inherent disadvantage of capacitor voltage drop during discharge, this approach offers a cost effective solution with sufficient energy for realistic testing. The new challenge is to provide bidirectional DC fault current flow during interruption, which is required with the latest LC DCCB topology [7]. Firstly, we will present the test circuit requirements and topology description. Then, we will discuss the selection of key test circuit components. Finally, a complete simulation model will be developed in PSCAD to analyse the operation of both the test circuit without and with the DCCB under various test conditions.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Fig. 1 depicts the schematic of the proposed DCCB test circuit, which has the following key requirements:

1) *Voltage ratings*: The circuit is designed to handle rated voltage of $V_{dc}=12$ kV. The peak voltage stress on the inductor reaches $V_l=18$ kV.

2) *Peak fault current*: The circuit should deliver a peak fault current of at least 6kA no earlier than 2ms after fault initiation.

3) *Fault current gradient*. The current gradient should be at least 2 kA/ms at 4 kA,.

4) *Fault Energy*: The circuit should provide at around 50-100kJ to adequately stress DCCB energy absorbers. This energy highly depends on the conditions in the real circuit and can not be readily predicted.

Fig. 1: Proposed DCCB Test System Schematic

5) *Circuit functionality*: The circuit topology should allow for DC fault current reversal when required. Importantly, voltage reversal should be strictly prevented, as typical MVDC systems are driven by VSC (Voltage Source Converter) which do not permit DC voltage reversal.

To achieve the given requirements, the design adopts a two-state approach: charging and discharging. The charging circuit utilizes a standard 50Hz, 240 V mains supply. As shown in Fig. 1, AC Circuit Breaker (ACCB) protects the circuit, while a Variac allows for adjustable charging voltage. A charging resistor R_c limits inrush currents during the charging process. The AC voltage is rectified to high DC voltage for charging the capacitor bank C_b through a full-bridge rectifier D_1 - D_4 and a step-up transformer. An additional resistor R_r connected on HVDC side protects the rectifier diodes during discharge.

Upon fault initiation, thyristor T_1 triggers the discharge circuit. The stored energy in the capacitor bank is discharged through the DCCB under test. Diode D_5 allows for fault current reversal if required by DCCB under test. Diode D_6 prevents capacitor voltage V_c reversal. A surge arrester (SA) protects switching components from overvoltage. The inductor L_{dc} with its inherent parasitic resistance R_{pL} regulates the rate of fault current rise as required for DC protection and DCCB sizing [2]. A safety discharge resistor R_d connected in parallel with a pilot LED R_{LED} provides a long-term discharge for the capacitor bank and enables visual monitoring of its charging level.

III. TEST CIRCUIT DESIGN

A. Discharge Circuit

1) *Capacitor C_b and Inductor L_{dc} Selection*: Analytical expressions for fault current during different stages, particularly the initial capacitor discharge stage (natural response), can be found in [9]. In this stage, the capacitor voltage v_c and current i_{dc} under the condition $R_p < 2\sqrt{L_{dc}/C_b}$ is expressed as:

$$v_c(t) \approx (v_c(0)/\omega_d)e^{-\alpha t} [\omega_d \cos(\omega_d t) + \alpha \sin(\omega_d t)] \quad (1)$$

$$i_{dc}(t) \approx (v_c(0)/L_{dc}\omega_d)e^{-\alpha t} \sin(\omega_d t) \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha = R_p/2L_{dc}$, $\omega_d = \sqrt{\omega_0^2 - \alpha^2}$, $\omega_0 = 1/\sqrt{L_{dc}C_b}$, $v_c(0)$ is the initial capacitor voltage and R_p is the total parasitic resistance of the current loop obtained as

$$R_p = r_t + R_{pL} + ESR + r_{dccb} \quad (3)$$

where r_t , R_{pL} , ESR , and r_{dccb} represent the on-state resistance of thyristor T_1 , and parasitic resistances of the inductor, capacitor and DCCB respectively. The rate of change of DC current in (2) is expressed as:

$$di_{dc}(t)/dt \approx (v_c(0)/L_{dc})e^{-\alpha t} [\cos(\omega_d t) - (\alpha/\omega_d) \sin(\omega_d t)] \quad (4)$$

Following the method in [10], initial selections were made as $C_b = 2\text{mF}$, and $L_{dc} = 4.4\text{mH}$. The capacitor bank will be implemented as a 30×3 matrix of 20 mF, 400 V aluminium electrolytic capacitors AIS71H203QT400 from KEMET, with the total energy of $E_{cb} = 144\text{kJ}$.

The natural frequency of the LC discharge circuit is calculated as $f_r = 1/2\pi\sqrt{L_{dc}C_b} = 53.7\text{Hz}$.

2) *Inductor L_{dc} Design*: The design of the inductor L_{dc} takes into account several key factors: skin effect, temperature rise, current profile and insulation.

a) *Skin Effect*: For the 4.4 mH inductor, a $1 \times 50\text{mm}^2$ single-core flexible PVC cable with a 204 A current rating and radius of 3.99 mm is selected. The skin depth is calculated using method in [11], as 9 mm. This is larger than the radius of the selected conductor, which suggests that the effective resistance is not much different from the DC resistance.

b) *Temperature rise*: The inductor temperature rise, ΔT ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), is estimated using the energy dissipated in the inductor, E_L (J), mass of inductor, m (kg), and specific heat capacity of the conducting material (copper), $c = 385\text{J/(kgC)}$.

$$\Delta T = E_L/(m \times c) \quad (8)$$

The energy dissipated in the inductor is obtained in PSCAD simulation using the inductor parasitic resistance R_{pL} .

c) *Current profile*: The total parasitic resistance in (3), largely affected by the capacitor's equivalent series resistance (ESR) and R_{pL} significantly influences the peak fault current. The first plot in Fig. 2 demonstrates this effect for the chosen components ($C_b = 2\text{mF}$ and $L_{dc} = 4.4\text{mH}$, using (2)).

Fig. 2 further investigates the influence of L_{dc} on the DC current and its derivative (di_{dc}/dt) using the same value of $C_b = 2\text{mF}$. It is seen that utilizing a higher inductance (6.7 mH) might not be optimal due to lower current derivative (1.3 kA/ms @ 4kA) and peak current (6.1 kA). However, with the selected inductance, 4.4mH, the desired current derivative (2.1 kA/ms @ 4kA) and peak current (7.4 kA) are achieved, satisfying our design requirement. Lower L_{dc} provides higher peak current, but the operating time is further reduced.

Fig. 2: Analytical current waveforms for different R_p and L_{dc} values.

The key design parameters for the air-core cylindrical inductor are presented in TABLE I. PSCAD simulation estimates around 116.3 kJ energy dissipation in the inductor considering worst case discharge with DCCB closed. The temperature rise is ΔT is 3.7°C, which is well within the selected cable's operating temperature range as specified in cable datasheet (40°C).

To ensure proper insulation for the expected 18 kV peak stress, we install inductor on a high-voltage platform and use insulation tapes between inductor layers.

3) *Thyristor T_1 and Diode (D_5 and D_6) Selection:* The semiconductors in the discharge circuit were selected based on three key factors: expected voltage stress 18 kV (1.5×12 kV), peak current stresses, and I^2t integral. T_1 is realised using three (3) infineon 7 kV/1 kA thyristors (T501N70TOHXPSA1) connected in series to provide ample current handling capability (13.5 kA peak surge current and 845 kA²s I^2t integral) and suitable voltage rating. Similarly, four (4) IXYS 4.5 kV/ 1.94 kA rectifier diodes (W1185LC450) and four (4) Infineon 4.8 kV/ 1.8 kA rectifier diodes (D1800N48) connected in series provide adequate current ratings and safety margins for Diodes D_5 and D_6 respectively.

4) *Capacitor Safety Discharge (R_d) and DC Resistor (R_r):* The discharge resistor is selected as R_d 800 k Ω , giving the time constant (5τ) for C_b discharge of 1600s..

The DC resistor $R_r=10 \Omega$ is employed to lower the fault current stress on the rectifier diodes (D_{1-4}) during discharge from 1.7 A to 0.6 A, allowing the use of lower rated and smaller diodes.

B. Charging Circuit

The charging circuit utilizes a commercial Variac (15A max. current), which facilitates testing at lower voltages. The selection of other key components is detailed below.

1) *Transformer and Diode Rectifier Selection:* The peak voltage at the transformer's secondary side $V_{s,pk}$ is given by $V_{s,pk} = \pi V_{rec}/2$ [2]. We use a 2 kVA transformer, with primary rating $V_{p,rms}=220$ V rms and $i_p=9.1$ A, and secondary

$V_{s,rms}=9350$ V rms and $i_s=0.215$ A, accounting for transformer and diode losses with a leakage reactance $X_{l,pu} = 0.2$ pu. The large capacitance ($C_b = 2$ mF) minimizes voltage ripple resulting in an average DC voltage close to the peak.

Each diode in the rectifier bridge will consist of three (3) series connected Diotec 6 kV/1 A diodes (BY6) to satisfy both voltage and current requirements.

2) *AC charging resistor R_c :* $R_c = 10 \Omega$, is selected to limit the initial charging current through the capacitor bank C_b and ACCB contactor. After a predetermined time (approximately 90 s), R_c is bypassed to speed up the charging process and boost the output DC voltage. Once the capacitor bank reaches the desired voltage level, the charging circuit is disconnected by simultaneously opening switches S_1 and S_2 . The ACCB remains closed by default and only trips upon overcurrent conditions.

TABLE I. TEST CIRCUIT PARAMETERS

Inductor Design Parameters	value, unit
Cable Size	1×50 mm ²
Cable insulation diameter	14.7 mm
Inductor core diameter	178 mm
Inductance	$L_{dc} = 4.4$ mH
Inductor parasitic resistance	$R_{pl} = 44.6$ m Ω
Number of turns	15
Number of layers	10
Total cable length	130 m
Total mass	m= 82 kg
Size (diameter × length)	472×221 mm
Energy dissipated in inductor	$E_l = 116.3$ kJ
Temperature rise	$\Delta T = 3.7$ °C
Charge and Discharge Circuit Parameters	
Capacitor bank	$C_b = 2$ mF
Total equivalent series resistance (ESR)	ESR= 120 m Ω
Transformer leakage reactance	$X_{l,pu} = 0.2$ pu
Capacitor discharge resistance	$R_d = 800$ k Ω
DC charging resistance	$R_r = 10 \Omega$
AC Charging resistance	$R_c = 10 \Omega$

IV. LC DCCB TEST OBJECT

A. LC DCCB Characteristics:

The test circuit is intended for testing wide range of DCCB topologies. In this study, the LC DCCB proposed in [7] is employed, and designed for typical 12kV MV applications. Its key components include ultrafast disconnecter (S_1), main capacitor (C_s), pre-charged capacitor (C_h) with trigger (T_1 and D_1) and charging circuit, energy absorber (SA_{cs}), and residual breaker (S_2).

B. DCCB Activation:

There are two methods to activate DCCB: direct signal appropriately timed, or using protection relay. It is desired that this DCCB test circuit facilitates also testing the DCCB protection relay, to provide realistic environment. In this study, protection relay will be utilized and the following thresholds for fault detection will be investigated:

- Threshold 1: 2 kA current threshold ($I_{dc,p} > 2$ kA) and
- Threshold 2: 5 kA current threshold ($I_{dc,p} > 5$ kA)

Further delays are added to account for sensor dynamics and relay processing. The key DCCB parameters are presented in TABLE II.

TABLE II. LC DCCB PARAMETERS

Protection Parameters	Label, value, unit
Current threshold 1	$I_{dc,p} = 2$ kA
Current threshold 2	$I_{dc,p} = 5$ kA
Relay processing delay	0.5 ms
Time to contact separation	0.5 ms
Residual breaker opening time	9 ms
DCCB Parameters	
Current at commutation (threshold 1)	$I_{cp} = 4.3$ kA
Current at commutation (threshold 2)	$I_{cp} = 6.6$ kA
Main capacitance	$C_s = 250$ μ F (18 kV)
Pre-charged capacitance	$C_p = 6000$ μ F (0.84 kV)
Arrester	$V_{ar} = 18$ kV, $E_a = 220$ kJ
Total parasitic inductance	$L_p = 4$ μ H
Total parasitic resistance	$R_p = 5$ m Ω

V. SIMULATION VERIFICATION

The model of the proposed test circuit and 12 kV LC DCCB, which follows the approach in [7] are developed in PSCAD and will be verified under certain conditions.

A. Charging Circuit: Capacitor Charging

Fig. 3 presents simulation of charging process:

- Initially, the charging resistor R_c limits the inrush current. After 90s, bypassing R_c speeds up charging and boost the capacitor voltage V_c (first plot). V_c peaks at 12.584 kV, slightly above its nominal 12 kV rating, which can be regulated with the Variac.
- The primary transformer current i_p (second plot) peaks at 27 A and the secondary current i_s (third plot) peaks at 0.64 A, which is well within the selected diode's 1 A rating. The power dissipation in R_c (fourth plot) peaks around 7.35 kW while its power rating is selected as 1 kW. This temporary overload is acceptable considering its datasheet specification.
- Full capacitor charging takes about 200s, confirming the circuit's ability to manage inrush current, power dissipation, and ensure effective capacitor charging.

Fig. 3: Test circuit charging responses.

B. Fault Current Simulation with DCCB Closed

Fig. 4 presents the responses of the discharge circuit with the DCCB closed. Initially, the capacitor bank is pre-charged to 12 kV. Thyristor T_1 is fired at $t=0.2s$ and key observations are summarized below.

- The peak DC current I_{dc} in the discharge circuit reaches 7.4 kA in about 4.4ms, although only 6kA is required. The current tails off in approximately 50 ms, with a current gradient of 2.19 kA/ms at 4 kA.
- The freewheeling current through diode D_6 (blue curve on third plot) peaks at 7.25 kA, while no current flows through the parallel diode D_5 (it only conducts negative current as required when DCCB opens).
- The simulation also assesses the energy capability of T_1 , D_5 and D_6 (black, green, and blue curves respectively on fourth plot). The I^2t integrals for T_1 (137 kA²s), D_5 (0 kA²s) and D_6 (2456 kA²s) are all within the limits specified in their datasheets (845 kA²s, 559 kA²s and 3781 kA²s respectively).

Fig. 4: Test circuit discharge responses with DCCB closed

C. Fault Current Simulation with DCCB opening

Fig. 5 presents the discharge circuit and DCCB responses when the DCCB opens. Thyristor T_1 is fired at $t=0.2s$ and DCCB protection relay sends trip signal after fault current I_{dc} exceeds the specified thresholds (2 kA and 5 kA). In Fig. 5a and b, the key observations are summarized as follows:

- Peak DC current I_{dc} reaches 4.89 kA and 6.7 kA for Thresholds 1 and 2 respectively. Diode D_5 conducts when I_{dc} changes polarity, while D_6 takes over when V_c attempts reversal. The DC current is observed to have an oscillating component, because of series LC circuit.
- The I^2t integrals for T_1 , D_5 and D_6 were found to be 43.4 kA²s, 7.4 kA²s, and 0.23 kA²s for Threshold 1, and 102 kA²s, 16.5 kA²s, and 7.28 kA²s for Threshold 2 respectively.
- The voltage across the inductor V_L peaks around 18 kV and settles at around 2.3 kV and 2.25 kV for Thresholds 1 and 2 and respectively. Therefore, some post-interruption stress is provided with the circuit.

(c) DCCB protection system operation for 2kA (top) and 5 kA (bottom) thresholds

Fig. 5: DCCB Test circuit responses when DCCB opens.

Fig. 5c outlines operation of protection relay and DCCB:

- The DCCB current I_{ufd} peaks at 4.3kA and 6.6kA for Thresholds 1 and 2 respectively (blue dashed curves) and drops to zero 0.5 ms after trip signal.
- The main breaker capacitor current I_c reaches 4.3kA and 6.6kA at commutation, peaking at 4.9 kA and 6.7 kA around 1ms and 0.7ms after trip signal for Threshold 1 and 2 respectively (black dashed curves).
- The breaker arrester current I_{arr} peaks at 4.1 kA and 5.6 kA, dropping to zero around 4.4ms and 3.9ms after the trip signal for Thresholds 1 and 2 respectively (green dashed curves).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the design and simulation verification of a 12 kV capacitor-based test circuit for DCCBs. The circuit has 144 kJ energy, providing peak current of around 7 kA, and facilitates current reversal during breaking. The PSCAD simulations validates the circuits performance, highlighting its ability to achieve effective capacitor charging and generate the required fault currents for DCCB testing. The post-fault voltage stress is lower than in real system, as with all capacitor-based circuits. The DCCB demonstrated reliable fault current interruption with peak values 4.9 - 6.7 kA within specified timeframes. Overall, the proposed test circuit offers a viable, and cost-effective solution for evaluating the performance of MV DCCBs in research laboratories.

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